

Emotional Attachment in Persona Design

Takashi Kiriya^{*1}, Hideaki Shirane^{*2}, Junko Nakamura^{*2}, Toyohisa Uehira^{*2},
Takuya Hirota^{*3}, Shizuka Moriguchi^{*3}, Yumi Hisanabe^{*4},
Yoshinobu Akimoto^{*5}, Yasuko Okada^{*5},
Yasuhiro Sasaki^{*6}, Hiroshi Miyazaki^{*6}, Shinji Takai^{*7}

**1 Tokyo University of the Arts, Yokohama, Japan*

kiriya.takashi@fm.geidai.ac.jp

**2 Daishinsha Inc., Tokyo, Japan*

**3 Sofia, Inc., Tokyo, Japan*

**4 Fujitsu Design Ltd., Kawasaki, Japan*

**5 Y2 Project, Tokyo, Japan*

**6 Mitsubishi Research Institute Inc., Tokyo, Japan*

**7 Doshisha University, Kyoto, Japan*

Abstract: In our research into how people form emotional attachment to a product and service, we found a few patterns by which attachment is formed. In a preliminary study, we designed questions that assist people reflect on their own attachment. Using the questions, we have found some patterns of attachment that can be described by desire and satisfaction. Such patterns can be included in the scenarios of personas.

Key words: *attachment, persona, pattern, design, emotion.*

1. Introduction

We feel attachment to things that have been with us for a long period of time. Examples of such emotional attachment include a vintage car that one does not want to release, a movie that one wants to view repeatedly, and a web portal that one wants to go even other portals may be better in functionality. Attachment to a product or service supports loyalty to the provider and thus better relationship with the user. Emotional attachment is a desired element of the design of products and services.

The authors are practicing the development of personas for product and service design. A persona is an imaginary person representing a particular segment of the user. A persona whose behavior is vividly described serves better understanding of the potential user than having an abstract idea of the user segment. Sharing personas in the design team establishes a consensus on the product needs, facilitates communication across the team, and promotes user consciousness. One of the authors, for instance, used personas of school kids and teachers for developing a Web portal of science to bridge the gap between the development team and actual users [1].

We create personas based on user research, including surveys, depth interviews, and site visits [2]. Such methods are useful to observe human behaviors [3]. To study emotional attachment, however, these methods have certain limitations. Because people are not always conscious of their own emotions of attachment, we may not be able to

find causal relationship leading to form an attachment. Using the same product for a long time makes it difficult to judge cost-benefit against other products or services. In such a situation, surveys and observations produce merely a collection of facts that are too specific to apply for other designs.

In our research into emotional attachment to a product or service, we try to find common patterns in which attachment is formed. In a preliminary study, we designed a set of questions that assist people in reflecting on their own attachment. Using the questions, we have found a few patterns of attachment that can be described in terms of desire and satisfaction. Such patterns may be included in a scenario of the behavior of a persona.

Attachment can be translated to "ai-chaku" in the Japanese language, meaning love and bonding. A Japanese dictionary defines the state of "ai-chaku" such that one cannot give up thinking of a person or an object. In this perspective, "ai-chaku" is of the same meaning as attachment, which derives from attach or fasten. Besides "ai-chaku", there is a related word "ai-jyaku". It means attachment too, with an implication of desire. "Ai-jyaku" is originally a Buddhism word referring to the human nature of attachment caused by desire. The Buddhism word "ai-jyaku" is of the same category as "ai-chaku", since they are spelled in the same Chinese characters. But its distinct pronunciation emphasizes desire found in attachment. In this study, we look at attachment by considering the two aspects of bonding and desire.

2. Emotional Attachment

2.1. Observing Emotions

Emotional attachment takes long time to form, typically for months to years. It puts attachment in a unique position among other emotions. For instance, Gross et al. studied elicitation of emotions using films [4]. Approximately 500 university students watched 78 clips taken from various films. They graded the clips in terms of the intensity of emotions, including joy, sadness, satisfaction, surprise, disgust, anger, and horror. The grades are statistically processed to identify the best movies that exclusively elicited the target emotion. The result showed that most emotions could have been elicited by viewing a clip for a few minutes. Anger was found to be difficult, however, to exclusively elicit using films. Another study shows that people feel angry with someone who critically reads their writing [5]. When they were asked to select a taste of drink for someone after being criticized, they tend to select the least tasteful one. This research indicates that anger too can be elicited in a short time if an appropriate social setting is provided.

Harris and Kampar have taken an up-to-date approach to study emotion [6]. In their "We Feel Fine" project, they have been collecting emotional statements found in blogs over the last five years. Sentences containing "I feel" or "I am feeling" are analyzed to extract an expression of emotion. Attributes of the blog's writer, including gender, age, and location, are also collected, if available. If the location is found, local weather at the time of writing is looked up in a weather database. By this process, who, what, when, where, and under what conditions are cataloged. Emotions found most frequently in blogs are better, bad, good, guilty, same, sorry, sick, followed by well, down, comfortable, great, happy, alone, and sad. These emotions are felt consciously and experienced in a relatively short period of time than attachment, so they are ready to be written in everyday blogs.

2.2. Reflective Questions

Unlike other emotions, attachment takes long time to form. Rather than responding to the stimulus from outside, as in the case of emotion elicitation using films, attachment relies on the memory that is accumulated through experiences. As Kahneman and Tversky showed by psychological experiments [7], evaluation based on memory is subjective, since memory itself is selective and incomplete. It means that to study attachment, we need to look at experiences in a person's memory, rather than in their responses.

Instead of showing video clips or mining blog data, we designed a set of questions to help the respondent reflect on the process of forming attachment. The questions, shown in Figure 1, are divided into two parts. The first part is intended to visualize the change of attachment, desire, and satisfaction over time. The respondent is asked to draw graphs on a piece of paper with a pencil and an eraser. The second part is intended to help analyze the cause of attachment. The respondent picks a particular product or service when answering the questions. The whole questions typically take a few hours to complete.

Part 1: Visualization

Please illustrate the changes of attachment, desire, and satisfaction with a product or service. Make a graph of the change of attachment, desire, and satisfaction for the entire period over the range of -10 to +10. Draw a line for each of attachment, desire, and satisfaction with a pencil. By drawing lines, remember major events that have influenced on your emotion. Adjust the shape of lines using an eraser.

A. Regarding the changes of lines in direction, curvature, inflection, and the repetition of shape;

- A1. What kind of event occurred?
- A2. What followed the event?
- A3. What did it mean to you?
- A4. How did you feel about the event?

B. Regarding the relationship among attachment, satisfaction, and desire;

- B1. What you do see in the relationship of these three lines?
- B2. Why do you think so?

C. Extend the lines to reach your best relationship to the product or service.

- C1. What do the changes in the extended part mean?
- C2. What kind of event do you expect to occur in the extended part?
- C3. What follows the event?
- C4. How do you feel about the event?

D. Suppose the lines in the entire period represent a story;

- D1. Divide the story into chapters.
- D2. Give a name to each chapter.

<p>Part 2: Analysis</p> <p>Please list as many causes as possible that formed your attachment by considering the personal and functional aspect, personal and emotional aspect, social and functional aspect, and social and emotional aspect.</p>
<p>E. For each chapter, pick out four most important causes.</p> <p>E1. Explain each cause in detail.</p> <p>E2. What kind of benefit did the causes bring to you?</p> <p>E3. What do you feel if the causes become true?</p>
<p>F. For each chapter, rate the causes 0 to 5 by their relationship to attachment, satisfaction, and desire.</p> <p>F1. What kind of links do you see between the causes and attachment, satisfaction, and desire?</p> <p>F2. Give another instance of your experience that is similar to the causes.</p>

Figure 1. Reflective Questions

3. Change of attachment

3.1. Mixi Apps

In preliminary research using the reflective questions, we found that people felt attachment with various things ranging from a hometown to a website. In this paper, we concentrate on two cases. The first case of Mixi was responded by a female designer. Mixi is the largest social networking service in Japan, with over 17 million registered members. Figure 2 depicts the graph of attachment, desire, and satisfaction that she originally drew on a piece of paper with a pencil. By her friend's invitation, she became a member of Mixi in October 2005. The lines indicate that attachment, satisfaction, and desire increased in the first 18 months. Then, the intensity of these emotions decreased, arriving at the lowest scores three years after joining. In the period of decreasing, she felt tired of writing diary. She also had other social networks to communicate with intimate friends.

Her attachment, however, increased again when she was invited by one of her friends to play a social game of Mixi application. A Mixi application (collectively called Mixi apps) is an add-on program provided by a third party developer. The game she played was a location game, in which players were supposed to move around in the real world. It made her to visit new places to collect game items. The application was so engaging that it became part of her life. Since she started to play Mixi apps, the level of satisfaction increased rapidly. Now she does not want to switch her mobile phone to iPhone, for example, because it is not capable of running Mixi apps. As we find in this case, attachment to the product or service and its ecosystem maintains loyalty.

Figure2. Attachment to Mixi

3.2. Korean Drama

The second case concerns the Korean TV drama. Since the great hit of a TV drama *Winter Sonata* in 2004, the Korean drama has been popular among Japanese women. Some of the Korean dramas consist of more than 80 episodes, making people watch one episode after another. The person who reported attachment to the Korean drama is a longtime cinema fan. At work she is responsible for public relations in a marketing consulting firm. Her attachment to Korean drama basically continued to rise over six months period, as shown in Figure 3. Occasional drops occurred due to;

- The drama she picked to view was not particularly interesting,
- Her work became too busy to view TV dramas, and
- Videos she wanted to rent in the holiday season were out of stock.

In answering the questions, she listed several causes of her attachment to the Korean drama, including;

- She became a fan of Il Song Gook, a famous actor,
- She repeats to watch her favorite scenes,
- The other dramas she started to watch were also interesting, and
- Watching TV dramas put away work pressure.

The fact that she found Korean dramas put away work pressure is notable, because it boosted her desire to watch Korean dramas as shown in the right hand of Figure 2. It does not mean that this situation is sustainable, because she does not feel satisfaction as much as desire.

Figure.3 Attachment to the Korean drama

4. Patterns of Attachment

4.1. Reviving Attachment

From the two cases above, we can extract some patterns of forming attachment. The first one is a long-term change of attachment (pattern 1). In the case of Mixi apps, attachment decreased once and increased again over the course of five years. In the low period, she hardly logged on and her blog was not updated. Such a falling of attachment can occur when the user is tired of the service. This situation was reversed when her friend invited her to play a social game application. It is apparent that introducing a new application to an existing service had changed the meaning of the user to the old service. It is also notable that third parties developers brought new applications to the social network service.

The change of attachment in a long timeframe may be used to extend a shorter time scenario. For instance, if the attachment to the Korean drama follows the same path as Mixi apps, it will continue to increase for the next six months and decreases until the next motivation arrives.

4.2. Attachment Supported by Satisfaction

The second pattern is a stable attachment supported by satisfaction (pattern 2). If we compare the two cases of Mixi apps and Korean drama, we find the level of satisfaction is different between them. In the Mixi case, after five years, attachment and satisfaction are both the highest. In Korean drama, attachment is around 6 in the scale of 10, which means that there is still a room for attachment to change. If the attachment to Korean drama wants

to become higher and stable as that of the Mixi apps, the level of satisfaction must be increased but not desire too much.

4.3. Attachment Preceded by Desire

The third pattern is a rise of attachment driven by desire (pattern 3). In case of Korean drama in Figure 3, the rise of attachment in the last few months is preceded by desire. The desire to watch TV dramas came from work pressure. In making a scenario for personas, we can add a pattern of strong desire caused by some reasons, leading to an increase of attachment. Note that such increase of attachment will not last long unless it is supported by the increase of satisfaction.

5. Augmenting a Scenario with Patterns of Attachment

A scenario for a persona can be augmented using patterns of attachment. As an example, we look at a scenario originally developed by one of the authors. This scenario is about a young woman who joined a fitness club. Figure 4 illustrates the course of scenario, consisting of nine episodes. Episodes 1, 2, 4, 8, and 9 are based on real stories some respondents replied in an Internet-based surveys. Although the five episodes are edited, they still maintain nuances found in the answers to the survey. Other four episodes, marked with * in Figure 4, were created by the analyst who wrote this scenario.

Figure 5 depicts the change of attachment, desire, and satisfaction in this scenario. The graph shows that episode 3 and 6 follow the pattern of attachment supported by satisfaction (pattern 2). Episode 5 and 7 follow the pattern of attachment preceded by desire (pattern 3). We trust that the analyst who created this scenario understood these patterns from experience and applied them for building a scenario of increasing attachment.

The scenario created by the analyst ends in episode 9. To extend the scenario beyond that point, we can follow a combined pattern of attachment driven by desire and satisfaction. It means that satisfaction should become higher and desire lower, so that attachment is maintained at a high level. We may develop an extended episode such that the instructor also plays a role of communication facilitator who eases her tension in the facility.

Figure 4. A Scenario for a persona joining a fitness club.

Figure 5. Attachment, desire, and satisfaction in the scenario of joining a fitness club

6. Conclusions

In our research into emotional attachment to a product or service, we try to find common patterns in which attachment is formed. In a preliminary study, we designed questions to guide people reflect on their own attachment. From the answers that we collected using the questions, we found a few patterns of attachment, including attachment over a long period, attachment supported by satisfaction, and attachment preceded by desire. The patterns can be incorporated in scenarios of the behavior of personas. These patterns of attachment are expected to allow personas easily extended to incorporate emotional aspects.

Future work includes gathering more patterns of attachment in both long and short timeframes. They should be tested in creating new scenarios. In addition to asking people about their experiences, analysis of existing scenarios should also be useful to find useful patterns.

7. References

- [1] Hisanabe, Y., Persona Marketing for Fujitsu Kids Site, Fujitsu Scientific & Technical Journal, Vol. 45, No.2, pp.210-218 (2009)
- [2] Pruitt, J., Adlin T., The Persona Lifecycle: Keeping People in Mind Throughout Product Design, Morgan Kaufmann (2006)
- [3] Kuniavsky, M., Observing the User Experience: A Practitioner's Guide to User Research, Morgan Kaufmann (2003)
- [4] Rottenberg, J., Ray, R. D., Gross, J. J., Emotion Elicitation using Films, in Coan, J. A., Allen, J. J. B. (Eds.), The Handbook of Emotion Elicitation and Assessment, Oxford University Press (2007).

- [5] Harmon-Jones, E., Amodio, D.M., Zinner, L, R, Social Psychological Strategies for Emotion Induction, in Coan, J. A., Allen, J. J. B. (Eds.), *The Handbook of Emotion Elicitation and Assessment*, Oxford University Press (2007)
- [6] Harris, J., Kamvar, S., *We Feel Fine: An Almanac of Human Emotion*, Scribner (2009)
- [7] Kahneman, D., *Maps of Bounded Rationality: Psychology for Behavioral Economics*, *The American Economic Review*, Vol.93, No.5, pp. 1449-1475 (2003)
- [8] Diller, S., Shedroff, N., Rhea, D., *Making Meaning: How Successful Businesses Deliver Meaningful Customer Experiences*, New Riders (2008)